

LETTER- MESSAGE, NOTE, WRITING

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Abstract. In the article, the meanings of letter, letter, and writing are expressed in terms of their specific function in fiction, as well as their use in the term of genres in Uzbek classical literature.

Keywords. Noma, letter, note, love letter.

The dictionary meaning of the word "Noma" is interpreted as a letter, letter, book, work, official correspondence. (3, 58) This word is combined with other words and acquires a terminological meaning. For example, added to the word "soqi", as a term of literary studies, it represents the name of a genre in the history of Uzbek literature. Sokinoma is a lyrical genre with a unique content structure and external form.

"Noma" is also used in the sense of writing. The word "acknowledgment" expresses such a meaning. Acknowledgment is a note expressing gratitude, recognition of the services of a person, official recognition. A whole word with the word noma in this place is not associated with fiction.

"Muhabbatnama" by Khorezmi is one of such works. The author writes this special love letter at the request of another person. The theme of the work is obvious from its name - the theme of love. However, the history of writing testifies that it had to be written in Uzbek. The author was asked to express the theme of love in Uzbek. The person who made the request was one of the officials of the khanate and he was also a poet. Stating that you have Persian notebooks in the world, the official begs, "My dear, our language will come out together and turn it into a book...". So, there is a social factor in the writing of "Muhabbatnama".

In fiction, a work written in the form of a letter addressed to another person is defined as epistolary literature as an independent genre. In general, many such works have been created in world literature, as well as in Russian literature. "Poor people" by F. Dostoevsky, "Vanka" by A. Chekhov, "Five pages" by K. Simonov in prose, "Letter to my mother" by S. Yesenin are examples of poetry.

In Uzbek literature, works of this type are called noma. Many examples of the noma genre are also created in Uzbek classical literature. Poems were written on love topics as well as on socio-philosophical topics.

An epistle can be part of a whole work. For example, Tatyana's letter to Onegin from A. Pushkin's "Eugene Onegin", Otabek and Kumush's letters from Abdulla Qadiri's novel "Otgan kunlar" are among the letters of the great work. It is customary to name a whole work with the addition of the word noma. For example, Muhammad Salih's "Shaibaniname" is one such work. But in this case, the term noma does not mean a letter, but in general it expresses the meaning of writing, story, narration. "Shahnama" is about the life of kings, "Shaybaniinama" is about the life of Shaybani people. In this genre, the events that the authors of this work have

written down for future generations are understood. In other words, "Shaybaniname" is a letter of Muhammad Salih about the events of his time.

In the history of Uzbek literature, the word noma is used as a component in the names of memoirs of the year-type type, i.e. in the form of "Boburnoma".

Letters on various topics were also written in 20th century Uzbek poetry. A. Oripov's poem "Letter to Descendants" is one such work. This poem begins with a direct image of time in relation to the earthquake that occurred in Tashkent in 1966.

Йўқ, яшай билмасман асримдан нари,

Даъво ҳам килмасман мангулик изга.

Балки бир кимсанинг унут дафтари,

Ногоҳон етказар шеърини сизга.

Unut's notebook tells about the place - the Tashkent earthquake, its consequences, people's work, perseverance, and courage in relation to time. A portrait of the impact of the disaster on the character and spirit of people is drawn. "The great disaster of our age" and the twice-repeated verses "Friends, it was a great tragedy" and "It was a terrible tragedy were really heavy" express the image of disaster.

"Letter to Generations" is written in time from the present to the coming time, to the future generation. It stays within one space by space, it is not sent to another space. In this poem, the letter has become an artistic detail in its broadest sense, as a means of conveying ideas.

M. Yu. Lermontov's poem "Letter" (translation by M. Shaikhzoda) also begins with a description of time.

Шамчирок ёқади... Титрок қўл билан

Ёзиб тугатардим сўнги жумлани.

Кулфатлар ва дардлар ҳолим қилиб танг,

Кўксимни қоплади ташвиш тумани ...

The letter is not addressed to contemporaries, nor to future generations, but it is a poem that begins as a begging and a plea to his lover, who claims to be "my soulmate". That's why these prayers remain prayers, the poet himself knows it well, in the whirlwind of hope and despair, at the same time, he says goodbye, he asks to see him once before leaving forever.

Умрбод алвидо! – Аммо, жонгинам,

Келгин бир ёнимга, келгин сўнги бор.

Жон чиқар нафасда бир оз бўл малҳам,

Кўзларимнинг ўти сўнсин беозор.

A poet who loves life and people wholeheartedly cannot find a meaningful relationship worthy of this innocent love. He sees happiness and loyalty in his poetry.

Алвидо! Шухрат деб беҳуда чопдим,

Оташин севдим, аммо бахрасиз.

Ҳар ёқда хиёнат ва заҳар топдим,

Вафони тополмадим созидан ёлғиз.

The following is observed in the contents of A. Oripov's "Letter to Generations" and M. Lermontov's "Letter":

1. In terms of size, "Letter to Generations", "Maktub" is fifty-six verses.
2. Both poems are written in eleven syllables, 6-5 rhythm. (This refers to the Uzbek translation of M. Lermontov's poem)

3. Both poems begin with an image of time.
4. A. Oripov's "Letter to posterity" was written for posterity - for the future. It describes the events and character of its time. M. Lermontov's "Letter" is addressed to his contemporaries, to one person, and there is a reference to the future. It expresses the experiences of a soul.
5. Both creators used the image of a letter as a detail in expressing their ideas.

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